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COMPUTATIONAL THINKING IN BASIC EDUCATION

A Teaching Methodology for Early Years of Elementary Education

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Master's thesis submitted to the State University of Bahia, in the Graduate Program in Biosystems Modeling and Simulation, as a partial requirement to obtain the title of Master in Biosystems Modeling and Simulation.

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Dedication

I dedicate this work to all the researchers who, even in the face of adversity and challenges, have persevered in their journey. With courage and a commitment to education and human development, you have made society a better place to live.

Abstract

Computational Thinking has emerged as an essential skill in Basic Education to address the challenges of the 21st century, fostering abilities such as logical thinking, critical reasoning, and problem-solving. Its implementation in early grades prepares students for an increasingly technological job market, as highlighted by the World Economic Forum and the Brazilian Computing Society (SBC), which emphasize its importance beyond programming. This study proposes a methodology for teaching Computational Thinking in the early years of Elementary Education, integrating Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and the use of Game Design Document (GDD) as pedagogical tools. The research is based on a systematic literature review, analysis of official documents such as the BNCC and Resolutions CNE/CP 02/2017 and CNE/CP 04/2018, as well as theoretical foundations like Piaget's Genetic Epistemology and neuroscientific evidence on learning. Additionally, the author's empirical experience contributed to the development of the proposed methodology. It is expected that the proposed methodology will support the teaching of Computational Thinking in public and private schools, fostering the development of essential skills for the comprehensive education of students.

Keywords: Computational Thinking. Neuroscience. Basic Education. Problem-Based Learning (PBL). Game Design Document (GDD)

Abbreviation List

PBL Problem-Based Learning

BNCC National Common Curricular Base

CIEB Brazilian Center for Innovation in Education

CNE National Council of Education

CS Computer Science

DCRB Bahia Referential Curriculum Document

INEP Anísio Teixeira National Institute for Educational Studies and Research

MSC Master in Applied Computing

CT Computational Thinking

PNE National Education Plan

SBC Brazilian Computer Society

UNEB State University of Bahia

OLPC One Laptop per Child

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

The advent of the digital age and rapid technological evolution have led to significant changes in how we live, work, and relate to one another. In this context, Computational Thinking has gained prominence as a fundamental skill for the 21st century, capable of preparing individuals to understand and solve problems in an engaging, creative, and critical manner. In this scenario, Computational Thinking (CT) has been highlighted as a skill that must be developed from childhood, just like reading, writing, and arithmetic Wing (2006). The relevance of Computational Thinking, comparable to the skills of reading, writing, and mathematics, lies in its capacity to foster fundamental cognitive competencies for the 21st century.

CT stimulates logical reasoning, problem-solving, creativity, and the ability to work collaboratively. These competencies are fundamental for dealing with the challenges of the digital world and for educating citizens capable of adapting and contributing to an ever-evolving society. Thus, recent studies indicate that CT has been continuously growing in the educational sphere Medeiros, Oliveira, and Santos (2021). Furthermore, mastery of Computational Thinking also favors success in various areas of knowledge, since its expertises are applicable in different contexts and are not restricted solely to the field of computing.

The incorporation of CT into basic education enables students to develop fundamental skills for the 21st century, which align, for example, with the competencies suggested by UNESCO (2015). These skills, also called "21st-century skills" or "key competencies for lifelong learning," encompass various areas of knowledge, as well as cognitive processes in the personal and social spheres. Among the essential competencies proposed by UNESCO, the following stand out:

Critical thinking and problem-solving: the ability to analyze information and situations objectively, identify problems, and develop effective solutions.

Communication: the ability to express oneself clearly and to understand others, using different forms of communication, both oral and written.

Collaboration and teamwork: the ability to work effectively with other people, respecting diversity and contributing to the achievement of common goals.

Creativity and innovation: the ability to generate new ideas, explore different perspectives, and seek innovative solutions to complex problems.

Digital literacy and ICT (Information and Communication Technology) competence: the ability to use digital and technological tools appropriately, as well as to analyze and evaluate information obtained through these resources.

Learning to learn: the ability to manage and organize one's own learning process, developing effective strategies and adapting to new situations.

Cultural and global awareness: the ability to understand and value cultural diversity and to engage in global issues with an informed and critical perspective.

Citizenship: the development of the skills and attitudes necessary to participate actively in society and contribute to collective well-being, promoting values such as justice, equity, and sustainability.

The competencies presented by UNESCO (2015) outline a fundamental set of skills that can be cultivated and enhanced through the integration of CT into Basic Education. In this context, it is important to note that many countries (e.g., Finland, Canada, Singapore, etc.) recognize the importance of these competencies and have initiated the implementation of public policies for their effective application in their educational systems. One example is the United Kingdom, which, since 2014, has incorporated computing and CT teaching into its national curriculum, spanning from elementary to high school, as highlighted by the UK Department for Education for Education (2013).

In the national scenario, Brazil is progressively aligning itself with international educational standards. With this objective, specific regulations on Computing have already been incorporated into the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) for Basic Education, encompassing both elementary and high school (CNE/CP No. 15, of December 21, 2017, and CNE/CP Resolution No. 2, of December 22, 2017) *National Common Curricular Base (BNCC, 2017)* (2017). This BNCC defines the cohesive and progressive set of learning that all students must cultivate throughout their academic journey.

The initial introduction of CT into the National Common Curricular Base was discreet and indirect, integrated into the mathematics curriculum, especially through the development of mathematical literacy. This literacy encompasses competencies and skills such as reasoning, representation, communication, and mathematical argumentation, fostering the establishment of conjectures and the formulation and solving of problems in diverse contexts. These learning

processes are pertinent for the advancement of essential competencies for mathematical literacy, as well as for the cultivation of CT da Educação (2018).

During this phase, as mentioned previously, the BNCC addresses CT discreetly and avoids explicitly mentioning it as a potential path to contribute to the specific and comprehensive cognitive development of students. This subtle inclusion highlights that, initially, the approach to CT was positioned as a complementary skill specifically within the scope of mathematical content, rather than being properly emphasized for its relevance in the context of Basic Education.

However, it is crucial to emphasize that during the year 2018, despite the preliminary inclusion of CT in the National Common Curricular Base, the publication of Resolution No. 4 of the National Council of Education (CNE/CP) on December 17 also occurred. This resolution complements the BNCC in the context of High School. In Article 18 of this document, the additional provisions regarding the contents and processes linked to the learning of Computing in Basic Education are reaffirmed (CNE/CP, 2018). This resolution marked the beginning of the recognition of the importance of CT and Computing teaching in Basic Education at the national level.

Thus, as a result of deliberations in the Chamber of Basic Education (CEB), the Indication CNE/CEB No. 3/2019 and the Ordinance CNE/CEB No. 9, dated December 11, 2019, led to the formation of a committee with the purpose of establishing specific guidelines related to the field of computing. These initiatives culminated in the formulation of the Guidelines for Computing in Basic Education, a supplement recently approved for the (BNCC), according to Resolution No. 1 of October 4, 2022 Brasil. Ministério da Educação (2022). This proposal is the result of a continuous effort by teachers from various disciplines related to computing in several federal units of Brazil, dedicated to teaching and researching Computing in Basic Education. The document was organized based on three pillars highlighted in the guide "Guidelines for Teaching Computing in Basic Education" de Computação (2024), which encompasses the pillars of CT, Digital World, and Digital Culture, detailed below:

CT: refers to the ability to understand, analyze, define, model, solve, compare, and automate problems and their solutions in a methodical and systematic way, through the development of the capacity to create and adapt algorithms, applying the fundamentals of computing to leverage and enhance learning and creative and critical thinking in diverse areas of knowledge. Digital World: involves learning about digital artifacts, encompassing both physical (computers, cell phones, tablets) and virtual elements (internet, social networks, and data clouds). Understanding the contemporary world requires knowledge about the power of information and the importance of storing and protecting it, understanding the codes used for its representation in different

informational typologies, as well as the forms of secure and reliable processing, transmission, and distribution. Digital Culture: involves learning aimed at conscious and democratic participation through digital technologies, which presupposes an understanding of the impacts of the digital revolution and its advances in contemporary society; as well as the construction of a critical, ethical, and responsible attitude towards the multiplicity of media and digital offerings, and the different uses of technologies and the content conveyed; as well as fluency in the use of digital technology to propose contextualized and critical solutions and cultural manifestations *XXXVIII Congresso da Sociedade Brasileira de Computação (CSBC 2018)* (2018).

In this sense, the Brazilian Government has been implementing public policies aimed at expanding and consolidating the insertion of CT in Basic Education, promoting the use of digital technologies in the educational process. A significant example of these policies is the recent approval of the National Digital Education Policy (PNED) by Law No. 14,533, of January 11, 2023. This legislation reinforces efforts to integrate computing and CT in basic education, establishing guidelines and actions in this direction. The PNED aims to reaffirm the importance of developing digital skills and computational thinking in the school curriculum. Together with the Norms on computing in basic education and the (BNCC), the policy aims to promote the integral development of the student throughout their educational trajectory.

In addition to all the aspects mentioned above, it is essential to emphasize that parallel to the implementation of the BNCC, Brazil experienced an important transformation in education with the establishment of the New High School. Law No. 13,415, of February 16, 2017, established a series of structural changes in High School, with the intention of making it more flexible, dynamic, and suited to the demands and interests of students, as well as the requirements of the job market and contemporary society. The new curricular structure is composed of the BNCC and specific formative itineraries, which encompass the areas of knowledge, allowing students to deepen their knowledge in areas of their interest.

This educational reform aimed to foster curricular diversification, interdisciplinarity, and the contextualization of content, promoting a more integrated and meaningful education for Brazilian youth. Given the implementation of the BNCC and this scenario of transformations in Brazilian high school, in harmony with national public policies, initiatives also occurred at the state level to align teaching with current educational guidelines. In Bahia, Ordinance No. 1978/2022 established the curricular organization of the School Units of the State Education Network that offer high school, according to the guidelines of the (DCRB).

This ordinance is based on Law No. 13,415, of February 16, 2017, which regulates high school in Brazil, known as the new high school. The purpose of this ordinance is to ensure the quality of teaching offered in the State Education Network of Bahia, through a well-structured curriculum

focused on the needs of the students. Ordinance No. 1978/2022 also emphasizes the *Deck of Knowledge Areas (Estações de Saberes)*, areas of knowledge that must be prioritized and developed throughout high school, aligning with the New High School and current demands.

The curricular organization of the formative itineraries for integral education comprises five itineraries: Languages and their technologies; Mathematics and its technologies; Human and Applied Social Sciences; Natural Sciences and Transdisciplinary Integrated Itinerary. All itineraries offer curricula with 7h and 9h daily. The workload for the common part of high school is 600h per grade, totaling 1,800 hours.

In all formative itineraries, there are three common curricular components: Scientific Initiation, Social Mediation, and CT. Furthermore, there are three *Decks of Knowledge Areas (Estações de Saberes)*: one focused on the area of knowledge, another on the identity territory, and one focused on transdisciplinary dialogue.

The *Complexos Integrados de Educação* (Integrated Education Complexes), established in Bahia, have their curricular organization based on the *Decks of Knowledge Areas (Estações dos Saberes)*. These decks prioritize the collective construction of knowledge, fostering student protagonism. The *Decks of Knowledge Areas* integrate active methodologies, promoting the autonomous, collective, and cooperative construction of knowledge, understandings, and practices. In this pedagogical model, the student assumes an active posture and the teacher acts as a guide for the activities, interfering as little as possible in the learning process.

In the current high school proposal in Bahia, according to the *Documento Curricular Referencial da Bahia* (Bahia Referential Curriculum Document), the *Decks of Knowledge Areas* aim to provide a transdisciplinary and integrated approach in the teaching-learning process Secretaria da Educação do Estado da Bahia (2022), playing a fundamental role in the construction of a holistic education. These decks are composed of ten distinct thematic areas, which promote interaction between different areas of knowledge, skills, and competencies. The ten *Decks of Knowledge Areas* are:

- I — Transdisciplinary Experiential Living and Practices: Scientific Initiation and Social Mediation;
- II — Corporealities;
- III — Entrepreneurship and Innovation with an emphasis on Territoriality;
- IV — Computational Thinking;
- V — Ecosystem and the Dynamics of the Relationship;

- VI — Ethics and the environment;
- VII — Identity, Belonging with an emphasis on Ethnic-Racial Relations;
- VIII — Knowledge of the Diaspora and Social and Human Rights;
- IX — Technical Professional;
- X — Technical Professional (DCRB, 2022).

Among the various decks, *Deck of Knowledge Areas IV* stands out in our research interests for addressing CT. Although the syllabi for each year of high school for this Deck are present in the DCRB document, it is noted that they present some repetition and there is no detailed course plan on how to develop them. Furthermore, CT is not treated as a possible means to enhance the cognitive processes of the learners. Therefore, we believe it is essential to review the current course plan, integrating CT in a more comprehensive and profound way into the teaching and learning process.

Considering the brief text mentioned above, and in view of the mentioned public policies, it is reasonable to deduce that the Brazilian educational scenario has sought to integrate computing, as well as CT into Basic Education, in response to a global trend in the realm of education. The state of Bahia, in turn, has striven to keep up with such changes.

In order to promote a comprehensive and effective approach to teaching CT, this dissertation proposes a methodology that seeks to unite the guidelines of the Norms for Computing in Basic Education, the opinion of the Norm on Computing in Basic Education as a supplement to the (BNCC), the Tables of Skills and Competencies approved by the (CNE), the foundations of neuroscientific knowledge about how the brain learns, the bases of Genetic Epistemology, and the empirical experience of the author.

The methodological proposal focuses on developing problem-solving skills, both in the context of machines and in the students' daily lives. It is understood that CT goes beyond programming and manipulating electronic devices, encompassing the ability to formulate questions, identify patterns, decompose complex problems into smaller parts, create algorithms, test and debug solutions, as well as evaluate the obtained results.

Considering the theoretical foundation in the norms for Computing in Basic Education, the neuroscientific perspective of learning, the principles of Genetic Epistemology, and the empirical experience of the author, the aim is not only to provide tools and techniques for teaching Computational Thinking but also to explore the potential for cognitive and metacognitive development of the students, providing them with a solid foundation for facing the challenges of the 21st century.

By adopting an integrated approach, this study seeks to contribute to the advancement of the educational field, providing theoretical and practical support for educators and educational policy makers interested in promoting the teaching of CT in the context of Basic Education. It is believed that the implementation of this methodology could result in students who are better prepared to face the technological and social challenges of the present and future, empowering them to become critical, creative, and participatory citizens in the digital society.

1.1 Problem

The problem that motivated the development of this work is related to: how to develop an effective methodology for teaching computational logic in elementary school (early years), with an emphasis on developing computational thinking, considering the context of basic education in Brazil?

1.2 Hypothesis

The use of (PBL), combined with the (GDD), contributes to the development of computational thinking in the early grades of elementary school, even in contexts with limited technological resources.

1.3 Motivation and Justification

The insertion of CT into basic education emerges as a topic of great current relevance and importance, given the constant progress of technology in society and its nature as a well-structured and well-defined way of thinking. However, the lack of clear guidance and an effective methodology for incorporating CT into schools, considering the stages of development and the aptitudes of the students, as well as brain functionalities, remains a constant and reiterated concern.

In this context, it becomes essential to first establish precise curricula and guidelines for the conceptual formulation and application of CT in basic education, as an initial requirement. Subsequently, the continuous training of educators regarding the genuine concept and purpose of CT, as well as its vigorous implementation in a teaching context, becomes crucial. This not only aims to enhance student engagement and cognitive performance but also seeks to promote an effective approach to problem-solving and thinking development, essentially using CT as an inherent neural tool or framework with broad applications in various fields and everyday

life situations, which include: problem-solving, decision-making, data analysis, creativity and innovation, critical thinking, collaboration, professional skills, automation and control, among others. CT, therefore, is not just a technical skill, but a mindset that promotes effective problem-solving in a wide range of contexts, logic, creativity, and analytical capacity.

In summary, this research is justified by the relevance of incorporating CT in a manner congruent with the contemporary demands of society. Furthermore, it arises from the need to structure a systematized and precise methodology for teaching computational logic, emphasizing Computational Thinking in the context of the early years of elementary school.

1.4 Scope Delimitation

CT is an increasingly important skill today. However, its incorporation into Basic Education is still incipient and lacks clear guidelines. Although Brazil has advanced in formulating public policies, as mentioned previously, to integrate Computational Thinking into Basic Education, there are significant challenges to be overcome, such as: the absence of a clear and concise methodology, the lack of continuous training for teachers, and the absence of adequate infrastructure in schools. These factors can hinder the effective implementation of a CT methodology in Basic Education. This is because it is not effective to have an assertive methodology if we do not have trained professionals to apply it assertively.

The delimitation of this study is restricted to the school environment and public and private elementary schools (early years). Furthermore, it focuses on the implementation of a methodology in the classroom and the evaluation of its effectiveness, whose objectives include providing training in Computational Logic for students, emphasizing Computational Thinking and its pillars, according to the aptitude of the children in each grade of elementary school (early years), as well as the pedagogical proposal of the institution. Specifically, this research concentrates on fifth-grade classes of elementary school, since covering all grades (1st to 5th) would require a more extensive and detailed analysis, unfeasible within the time available for the completion of this work.

1.5 Objectives

General Objective

This research aims to propose a methodology for teaching CT in the early years of elementary school, using the development of GDD as a strategy. The approach seeks to make the principles

of CT accessible and suitable for the children's cognitive level, promoting logical reasoning, problem-solving, creativity, and computational logic.

Specific Objectives

- (I) Elaboration of the methodology for the development of computational thinking focused on the development of GDD in children in elementary school (early years);
- (II) Adaptation and creation of playful and interactive pedagogical strategies that involve children in the computational thinking learning process.

1.6 Structure of the Defense Project

The outline of the defense project is structured in accordance with the following chapter organization: Introduction, Theoretical Foundation, and Methodology. The Introduction will systematically and comprehensively address the motivation underlying the research, its justification, identification and delimitation of the research problem, as well as the general and specific objectives aimed for. In turn, the Theoretical Foundation will be intended for the in-depth analysis of the history and concept of CT, encompassing its four fundamental pillars. Additionally, the interfaces between Computational Thinking and Neuroscience will be explored, with an emphasis on understanding the cooperative interaction between such domains, highlighting neuroscientific evidence that supports learning based on practical and collaborative activities, in addition to theoretical approaches such as Piaget's Genetic Epistemology. The application of pedagogical methods such as the Game Design Document (GDD) and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) in teaching CT will also be discussed. The Methodology chapter will be dedicated to the detailed exposition of the adopted methodological choices, the structure of the database used in the research, the specific instruments used for data collection, the plan for data collection and analysis, the research schedule, the meticulously elaborated work plan, and the tools used to validate the effectiveness of the proposed methodology.

1.7 Alignment

This dissertation focuses on computational modeling applied to the teaching of Computational Thinking (CT), with an emphasis on the use of the Game Design Document (GDD) as a tool for representing, analyzing, and simulating cognitive and pedagogical processes. It is aligned with the area of Modeling and Simulation of Biosystems (AC) and the research line Modeling

of Biological and Educational Systems (LP) of the PPGMSB, whose main objective is to propose, analyze, and validate computational models that describe, interpret, and simulate complex behaviors in biological and educational systems. The study was developed at the *Núcleo de Pesquisa em Modelagem e Simulação Educacional* (NUMSE), specifically analyzing how computational thinking processes—decomposition, abstraction, pattern recognition, and algorithms—can be formalized into computational models that represent reasoning and learning in school contexts.

Reviewing the history of the PPGMSB, 12 dissertations and 5 theses related to this study were identified. The works closest to the theme of this dissertation are listed in Table 2.1.

The main contribution of this study is the proposition of a teaching methodology based on the computational modeling of cognitive and pedagogical processes, using the GDD as a formal structure of representation and Computational Thinking as a theoretical and practical basis. The proposed methodology integrates modeling, simulation, and educational design, allowing the computational representation of the reasoning steps involved in creating games and learning activities. This integration strengthens the link between Education, Computing, and Neuroscience, by demonstrating how modeling can support the understanding of the mental mechanisms involved in learning and solving complex problems.

The study provides subsidies for future research in computational modeling of cognitive processes, simulation of learning environments, development of pedagogical agents, and intelligent educational technologies. It also contributes to the consolidation of the educational modeling area as a subfield of biosystems modeling, by exploring the parallel between biological and cognitive systems.

The work is aligned with the advisor's research project, entitled "Modeling and Simulation of Cognitive Processes in Learning Environments", whose central objective is to develop and validate computational models that represent reasoning, memory, and learning processes in formal and non-formal teaching contexts. Furthermore, the proposal is in tune with the program's strategic planning and rigorously follows the methodological and epistemological guidelines established by the advisor.

Finally, the study addresses issues related to quality education and cognitive sustainability, contributing to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). By proposing a teaching methodology that combines modeling, simulation, and the development of cognitive and digital skills, this work is positioned to achieve the SDG goals 4 (Quality Education), 9 (Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure), and 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities).

1.8 Relevance of the Study

A model, as applied in this research, enables an innovative approach to teaching Computational Thinking (CT) in Basic Education, promoting more accessible and meaningful learning. Therefore, the relevant points of this study are:

1. Reduction of the gap between the passive use and active appropriation of technology by students;
2. Development of essential competencies, such as logic, abstraction, and problem-solving, from the early grades of Elementary School;
3. Integration of the Game Design Document (GDD) and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) as innovative strategies in teaching CT;
4. Democratization of access to computational knowledge, making it more aligned with the students' cognitive level;
5. Stimulation of creativity, innovation, and active participation in the digital society.

2.1 Theoretical Basis

This research is dedicated to investigating CT. The methodological approach employed includes a comprehensive review of national and international literature, aiming to assess the current state of development in this specific field of study. This section presents the results of the systematic literature review, which encompass the preeminent conceptual models and significant findings in the sphere of CT. Additionally, the importance of understanding the fundamental cognitive structures for the development of CT is emphasized. This understanding is crucial for the elaboration of a consistent teaching methodology. In this context, this analysis is grounded in the theory of genetic epistemology, which deals with the genesis and evolution of thought, and incorporates insights from contemporary studies in cognitive neuroscience and how the brain learns. This multidisciplinary approach aims to provide a solid foundation for the investigation and application of effective pedagogical strategies in the context of CT.

The recognition of CT as a fundamental skill in the 21st century has driven the development of innovative pedagogical strategies for its introduction from the initial phases of education, that is, from the foundation of human formation. In this context, a teaching methodology for computational logic aimed at students in the early years of Elementary School is proposed, considering both the development of CT and the development of the child's cognitive aptitudes, based on neuroscientific insights that guide education, how the human brain develops, and how this brain creates and solves problems based on its logical and abstract readiness when organized and flexible. Understanding the structuring and evolution of the brain from elementary abstractions to more complex ones constitutes the starting point for proposing activities, challenges, and problems that are aligned with the children's cognitive competencies. Such an approach aims to instigate active engagement, fostering the progressive development of mental capacities and providing an environment conducive to learning.

The theoretical basis of this methodology is anchored in the contributions of renowned authors and researchers in the field of CT. Jeanette Wing, a pioneer in defining the term, provided a solid understanding of the concept. Resnick et al. (2007), through the Scratch educational programming environment, demonstrated how CT can be fostered through creativity and exploration. The collaboration between Papert and Solomon (1971) and Papert (1980) in creating the Logo environment highlights the importance of starting CT from an early age. This methodology also adopts a project-based and exploratory approach, in line with the contributions of Andrea diSessa, who recognizes analogy and modeling as ways to facilitate young learners' understanding of complex computational concepts. Brennan and Resnick (2012), in turn, encourages creativity and personal expression in computational learning. The proposal aligns with the focus of Grover and Pea (2018) on assessing the development of CT, ensuring an efficient approach.

The methodology similarly integrates insights from cognitive neuroscience, incorporating the research of authors such as Dehaene (2022a), who explores the foundations of mathematical learning in the human brain. The contributions of Lent (2019) and Izquierdo (2018), which elucidate how learning occurs at the neuronal level, provide a basis for designing effective pedagogical strategies. The perspective of Jean Piaget in considering the stages of cognitive development when planning teaching in the construction of concepts and mental operations, as well as the works of Cosenza and Guerra (2011), Relvas (2017) and Amaral and Guerra (2022) in neuroeducation, which emphasize the importance of considering individuals' aptitudes so that skills and competencies adequate to their capacities for abstracting information and solving problems are developed. Furthermore, Erik Kandel's approach to studying the neuronal mechanisms underlying learning enriches the methodology by supporting the understanding of the formation of brain connections during learning.

The proposed methodology for teaching computational logic with an emphasis on CT, enriched by the contributions of the aforementioned authors, in addition to being supported by neuroscientific knowledge, offers an innovative approach to prepare students in the early years of Elementary School for current and future challenges. By creating an educational environment that encourages exploration, problem-solving, creativity, and cognitive development, this methodology strives to promote a deep understanding of computational logic, thus contributing to the formation of more capable individuals in today's technological world.

2.2 Brief History of CT in Education

The introduction of coding in education began with the pioneering work of Seymour Papert, who combined Jean Piaget's learning theories with the Logo programming language developed by him at MIT in the 80s Kafai (2006). Papert believed that computer programming could assist in children's learning process, especially regarding problem-solving.

In 2010, the President of Fast-Future, Rohit Talwar, stated that most professions were evolving to include technology and become increasingly multidisciplinary Talwar (2010). Fast-Future, commissioned by the British government, conducted one of the most comprehensive studies on global labor market trends, consulting 486 experts from 58 countries. In addition to noting changes in existing professions, the research also predicted the emergence of 110 entirely new careers by 2050.

The technological proliferation in this decade is undeniable, with artificial intelligence evolving from science fiction to reality. The computer can now see, hear, and even drive vehicles with a capacity approaching that of humans and may eventually equal or surpass it in the future Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2014). Technology is evolving more and more, bringing both serious problems such as unemployment and stagnation, and opportunities for innovative ventures.

Thus, the importance of education and preparation for the real-digital world, which is increasingly present in society, can be observed. Technological evolution brings with it the need to possess skills, competencies, and knowledge related to technology, and CT is precisely one of these relevant aspects.

The publication of an article by American researcher Jeannette M. Wing (2006) resulted in the term CT at the international level, which conceptualizes it as an essential skill, comparable to reading, writing, and arithmetic, for all people, particularly for children, regardless of their relationship with the computing field.

When dealing with CT, among the main concepts used are problem modeling using abstractions, dividing problems into smaller parts, designing solutions through sequential steps (algorithms), and identifying patterns. According to Wing (2008), in problem-solving, the solution can be executed by a human or a machine, or even by combinations of humans and machines. In the last decade, CT has become a tool for solving problems in virtually all areas of knowledge and has changed the way sciences are thought about.

CT practices do not intend to make humans think like computers, but seek to represent how humans, not computers, think and seek to solve problems. CT should be stimulated from an early age, just like writing, reading, and arithmetic Wing (2008). Meanwhile, Blikstein

(2008) highlights that CT contributes to the increase of cognitive power and creativity, enabling benefits for learning and the way of seeing and understanding the world.

Considering the implementation of CT in Basic Education, Wing (2008) raises a question of great relevance to scholars about how to teach and learn CT, as well as how and when people should learn this type of thinking and how and when we should teach it. At that time, the researcher already predicted that CT would be an integral part of basic education and also left a warning regarding the existence of many cultural, economic, political, and social barriers to the realization of this vision, especially in countries where the educational system is not centrally controlled and guides an effort towards the realization of her prediction as a great benefit for society in general.

Considering the reality and the strong influence of computing today, Wing (2011) brought us important reflections on the fact that CT is everywhere and states that this condition affects everyone directly or indirectly. This view again highlights the importance of its learning, being an essential knowledge not only destined for a minority, but rather, it should be offered to everyone and in different areas of knowledge. On this point, the author emphasizes that the promotion of CT stands as an educational challenge.

With this trend, CT practices have been introduced not only for university courses: they now also extend to Basic Education. Many researchers point out the importance of working on CT from Early Childhood Education, considering the technological reality of world society.

Analogous to learning reading and writing, CT is an important advancement. In this context, people not only learn to use technology but also understand how computational devices and systems work. Furthermore, CT involves applying cognitive skills to deal with everyday situations, becoming a comprehensive and valuable approach to facing challenges in the modern world.

The implementation of CT in education can contribute to the development of critical and analytical thinking, essential skills in today's world, characterized by the rapid evolution of technologies and the constant production of information. The United Kingdom in 2014, as a consequence of these trends, made the teaching of computer programming compulsory in basic education, including this discipline in the national curriculum for students from the age of five The Royal Society (2012).

This was the starting point for other leading countries in the educational ranking, such as Finland, Canada, Singapore, Italy, China, and many US states, to adopt the inclusion of CT in their curricula Voogt, Fisser, Good, Mishra, and Yadav (2015). In recent years, countries like Australia, Greece, India, South Korea, Germany, France, and Japan offer this new component

optionally and/or in pilot schools, most with deadlines already set to make it compulsory Bocconi, Chiappini, Dell'Anna, and Ferrari (2016).

Brazilian initiatives for the introduction to CT have been conducted by researchers from schools and higher education institutions, both public and private, at different levels of school education. Analyzing the last ten years, it is possible to highlight various studies and proposals. Barcelos and Silveira (2012) discuss the importance of CT in the training of Mathematics and Computing teachers, while Scaico, Oliveira, and Fuks (2015) address the inclusion of CT in the training of Informatics teachers.

In 2013, França and Amaral presented a teaching model for CT for elementary school. Ribeiro, Silva, Barrère, and Silva (2013) highlight the importance of including CT in elementary school Mathematics classes, and Barreto (2013) emphasizes the relevance of CT in the training of Mathematics teachers. Andrade, Araújo, Chagas, and Silveira (2016) propose a teaching approach for CT in basic education. Silva (2023) and SBC SOL (2023) discuss the inclusion of CT in the training of Mathematics teachers; until this moment, the focus of CT was directed mainly towards mathematics teaching.

A proposal for teaching CT for basic education emerges with Campos, Silva, and Silva (2014). Already in 2016, Kologeski, Silva, and Costa (2016) propose a game-based approach for teaching CT in high school. The *Centro de Inovação para a Educação Brasileira* (CIEB) began talking about the implementation of CT in Brazil in 2016, when it launched the document "Computational Thinking in Basic Education: why and how to insert it", which presented the principles and guidelines for the introduction of CT in Brazilian basic education. Since then, CIEB has been a reference for discussions and initiatives related to the implementation of CT in the country.

Researcher Brakmann (2018) is another important name in the study of CT in Brazil, especially in the development of unplugged activities, which do not depend on computers or digital technologies. In his research, Brackmann argues that unplugged activities are an efficient way to introduce programming and CT concepts to students, in addition to being more accessible in places with poor infrastructure. These initiatives seek to accelerate the process of adopting programming classes in the curriculum matrix of schools in different regions of the country; however, they lack depth on how to carry out this process and distance themselves from the discussion of how CT can support learning.

Considering the importance of integrating CT as an approach to enhance education in its entirety, it is essential to deepen the understanding of the fundamentals that support this methodology. This involves analyzing the main pillars of CT and how they can be applied both in activities that use technology and in those that do not. Thus, the next section will explore

the four pillars of CT. This analysis aims to enrich the debate on the implementation of CT in learning.

2.3 Computational Thinking and its Four Pillars

CT, short for "thinking like a computer scientist" refers to the ability to understand the underlying notions and mechanisms of digital technologies to formulate and solve problems. This definition reflects that proposed by Wing (2017), who states that CT is the thought process involved in formulating a problem and expressing its solution(s) in such a way that a computer—human or machine—can effectively carry it out. This perspective is clearly rooted in the concepts and practices of Computer Science (i.e., thinking like a computer scientist) proposed as an intellectual framework for thinking. Therefore, CT is based on four main pillars, which work together to promote the development of this cognitive skill, they are:

Decomposition: Decomposition involves breaking down a complex problem into smaller, more manageable parts. This pillar is crucial in CT, as it facilitates the analysis and solution of complex problems in a systematic and efficient manner.

Pattern Recognition: Recognizing patterns means identifying similarities, differences, and trends in data or problems. This pillar is fundamental in CT, as it assists in identifying efficient solutions and creating more effective algorithms.

Abstraction: Abstraction consists of simplifying complex problems by removing irrelevant details and focusing on the most important aspects. This pillar is vital in CT, as it allows for the creation of simplified models and representations of real-world problems that can be solved efficiently.

Algorithmic Thinking: Algorithms are sequences of steps or instructions that lead to the solution of a problem. Mastering algorithms is a fundamental skill in CT, as it allows for the development of effective solutions to complex problems and the automation of repetitive tasks.

Based on the four main pillars of CT—decomposition, pattern recognition, abstraction, and algorithmic thinking—it becomes evident that there is a need to integrate these cognitive skills into the educational process. Thus, it is crucial to investigate how the human brain learns and assimilates these concepts to optimize the application of CT in teaching. In this context, the next section will address the relationship between neuroscience and learning, in order to better understand how the human brain processes and integrates the skills associated with CT and thus maximize its potential in teaching and learning.

2.4 Definition of CT and Comparative Analysis of Teaching Methodologies in International and National Contexts

To enhance the understanding of the CT concept and analyze its methodological structure, both globally and in Brazil, a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) was conducted, addressing the theme in international and national sources. It is worth emphasizing that, aiming to expand the systematic review and include significant works on CT teaching methodology, an exception was made to include analyses of curricula in Spanish, thus encompassing the Latin American context. The SLR objectives were guided by questions such as:

- 1 - What are the main concepts that underpin the term CT?
- 2 - How have CT skills been developed in children and young people?
- 3 - Are there teaching methodologies endorsed by the scientific community on CT internationally and in Brazil?

A search for international sources was conducted on the CAPES journal portal and ERIC (Education Resources Information Center) over the last 5 years, with a limit in 2021, corresponding to the beginning of this dissertation project. For national sources, the Brazilian Symposium on Informatics in Education (SBIE) and the Workshop on Informatics in Schools (WIE) were consulted from 2018 to 2021. It should be noted that the search for national studies was limited to this period due to the scarce quantity of studies prior to 2017 in the Brazilian scientific literature (Carvalho et al., 2017).

For the research, articles that included the search terms "Computational Thinking", "Computational Thinking and Education" or "Computational Thinking and methodology" were selected. The terms were applied to the metadata of published articles, and for searches in Brazilian repositories, the same terms in Portuguese were used. Works in languages other than English or Portuguese (Brazil) were discarded. After applying the filters, 74 results were obtained, of which 21 were discarded for not presenting a methodology or not delving into the results, affecting question 2.

Subsequently, 25 articles were removed for not describing their methodology or the development of projects, activities involving CT, or suggestions for appropriate methodologies in basic education, affecting questions 2 and 3. Finally, 28 articles were selected and read in full.

A national search was conducted, resulting in a set of works that met the criteria of removing superficial articles, those without a consistent bibliographic basis, or that did not address our interests regarding CT, according to the criteria described in the international search. 14

studies were selected, analyzed, and synthesized to address the questions proposed in this review. Below, Table [ref] shows the systematized results of the Systematic Review:

Tabela 2.1: Systematized Results of the SLR. Source: Author (2023)

Authors	Year	Country	Study Focus
Kalelioğlu et al.	2016	International	CT Activities
Kafai	2016	International	CT Activities
Weintrop et al.	2016	International	CT Skills
Wing.	2017	International	Main Challenges
Bilbão et al.	2017	International	CT Assessment
Corradini, A et al.	2017	International	Case Study - Scratch Usage
Shute, V, J., et al.	2017	International	CT Skills
Cooper	2017	International	Activities
Denning.	2017	International	CT Assessment
Yasar.	2018	International	New Perspectives on CT
Grover, S & Pea, R.	2018	International	Activities
Bers	2018	International	Scratch Usage
Basogain et al.	2018	International	Case Study: Hybrid Teaching
Kale et al.	2018	International	Teacher Training
Haseski et al.	2018	International	CT Skills
Ching et al.	2018	International	Main Resources
Zhang, J. & Nouri, J.	2019	International	SLR
Kruger, L. & Pinkwart, N	2019	International	CT Skills
Román-González, M. et al.	2019	International	CT Skills
Yağci	2019	International	CT Assessment
Huang, W. & Looi, C.k.	2019	International	CT with Scratch
Eickelmann, B. et al.	2019	International	Twelve CT Skills with Scratch
Palts et al.	2020	International	CT Skills
Pérez-Marína et al.	2020	International	Twelve
Olmo-Muñoz et al.	2020	International	Case Study
Tang et al.	2020	International	Case Study: Plugged / Unplugged Activities
Esteve-Mon et al.	2020	International	Teacher Training
Israel-Fishelson, L. et al.	2021	International	CT Skills
Guarda & Goulart	2018	Brazil	Case Study – Unplugged Activities
Silva & Javaroni	2018	Brazil	Case Study – Educational Robotics
Ortiz & Pereira	2018	Brazil	CT Activities
Pires et al.	2018	Brazil	Case Study - Scratch Narratives
Cunha & Nascimento	2018	Brazil	Case Study – Unplugged Activities
Guarda et al.	2018	Brazil	Case Study – Unplugged Activity
Martinelli & Sakata	2018	Brazil	Case Study – Unplugged and Plugged Activities
Mattos et al.	2019	Brazil	Case Study – Unplugged Activity
Severgnini & Soares	2019	Brazil	Case Study – Workshop with CodeCombat
Souza &	2019	Brazil	Case Study – Gamification Workshop
Santana & Pereira	2019	Brazil	Case Study – Unplugged and Plugged Activities
Guarda et al.	2019	Brazil	Case Study – Scratch Workshops
Santana & Oliveira	2019	Brazil	Case Study – Scratch Workshops
Silva et al.	2019	Brazil	Case Study – Scratch Workshops with Arduino

Regarding Question 1, the SLR of studies addressing CT allowed for the identification of the main concepts that underpin this term. According to the research, various international authors associate the concept of CT with the development of skills such as: problem-solving, abstraction, decomposition, pattern identification, algorithm design, and error debugging.

In the Brazilian context, the term CT is supported by multiple concepts that also permeate the foundations of CT, including algorithms, logic, abstraction, decomposition, pattern recognition, automation, and generalization. These concepts are essential for understanding CT and have been widely discussed in contemporary literature.

However, despite the existence of numerous studies on the subject, there is still no single, consensual definition of the concept of CT. Definitions and approaches vary considerably, depending on the author, the field of knowledge, and the educational context in which they are situated.

In summary, the literature review on the subject of CT enabled the identification, in the literature, of three main areas of definitions for this concept, which are: Firstly, CT can be understood as a form of thinking that seeks to develop solutions that can be processed and executed by a computational agent. This definition encompasses the recognition of aspects of real-world problems suitable for computational formulation Corradini et al. (2017); Eickelmann et al. (2019)).

Secondly, CT is perceived as a thought process applied in problem-solving (Grover and Pea (2018); Huang and Looi (2020); Zhang and Nouri (2019)).

Lastly, CT is defined as a thinking skill that can be transferred and applied to solving real and meaningful problems in various contexts and disciplines, using algorithmic methods (Israel-Fishelson et al. (2021); Román-González et al. (2019); Shute et al. (2017)).

The diversity of definitions for CT in the literature is highlighted by Bocconi et al. (2022), who state that researchers tend to base their investigations on different definitions. This results in distinct perspectives when applying, interpreting, and evaluating CT concepts and their related practices. The identification of these gaps and convergences among studies contributes to a better understanding of the concept of CT and its implications in the educational field.

The analysis presented in relation to Question 2 of the SLR identifies the existence of different approaches regarding the development and application of CT by young people and children in different contexts. While the majority of international studies involve digital activities, in Brazil analog activities are more common, due to socioeconomic and school infrastructure issues. Furthermore, most experiments occur in Elementary School, especially from the 5th grade onwards, and no studies were found involving preschool children, 1st to 3rd grades of

Elementary School, and High School, which points to the need for investment in the education and training of young people regarding CT.

The analysis of studies on CT indicates that most activities are directed at Elementary School, mainly from the 5th grade onwards. However, the systematic review did not find studies involving preschool children, 1st to 3rd grades of Elementary School, and High School. This gap highlights the need for investment in educator training and student education regarding CT, which should be seen as an opportunity for the integral development of students, complementing their cognitive skills and preparing them for a world where technology and humans live almost in symbiosis. The table below presents the macro-categories that group the concepts associated with CT identified in the literature:

Tabela 2.2: Classification of CT concepts into three macro-categories. Source: author, 2023.

Categories	Definitions
Generic Definitions	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. CT refers to the mental processes necessary to create a problem and articulate its solution(s) so that a computational agent can successfully execute it (GROVER & PEA, 2018).2. The application of CT is independent of technological means and involves cognitive processes (HAZZAN et al., 2020).3. CT is described as a problem-solving technique that uses basic programming skills Zhang and Nouri (2019).
Practical Definitions or Models	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. The CT framework involves solving problems, building systems, and understanding human behavior using central notions of computer science Jocius et al. (2020).2. CT is a collection of abstract problem-solving skills with broad applicability Huang and Looi (2020).3. CT comprises eight fundamental components such as abstraction, evaluation, generalization, among others Komm et al. (2020).4. Classifies CT concepts into four major categories: data analysis and structuring, modeling and simulation activities, computational problem-solving practices, and systemic thinking practices Waintrop et al. (2016).

From these results, it is possible to observe the existence of gaps in the incorporation of CT into education, especially regarding the lack of studies involving preschool children, 1st to 3rd grades of Elementary School, and High School. Furthermore, the absence of a single, consensual definition for the concept of CT may hinder the proper application and evaluation of CT in different educational contexts. On the other hand, the diversity of approaches and concepts related to CT can be seen as an opportunity to explore different perspectives and enrich the understanding and practices related to CT.

Regarding Question 3, no studies were found that directly address the topic. However, it is possible to identify international and national curricula that work with the development of

CT in their educational strategies. One example is the Digital Technologies Curriculum from Australia, which aims to work on CT skills together with other technology-related competencies, preparing students for the technological demands of today's world ACARA (2021).

In the United States, Code.org is a non-profit organization that developed a curriculum to be used by Elementary and High School students, aiming to expand access to computer science education, especially for girls and underrepresented groups Code.org (2024). In the European Union, the European Digital Competence Framework (DigComp) is a reference for the development of digital competencies of European citizens, including CT. The framework is divided into five competency areas: information and media literacy, communication and collaboration, digital content creation, safety, and problem-solving Commission (2017).

In Latin America, some countries have already developed curricula and methodologies to work on CT in their educational strategies. Colombia, for example, developed the "Plan Nacional de Tecnologías de la Información y las Comunicaciones en Educación - 2008-2019"(National Plan for Information and Communication Technologies in Education - 2008-2019), with the main objective of training students in the technology area, including programming and robotics. Subsequently, Peru also developed a curriculum in 2016, applied in public and private schools across the country.

The curriculum was developed with support from the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) and Harvard University, and plans to train students capable of using technology to solve real-world problems, incorporating programming, robotics, and CT. In Mexico, the National Digital Strategy, launched in 2017, establishes the government's commitment to promoting CT in basic education, and several Mexican universities and educational institutions have developed programs and projects to train teachers and students in this area, with emphasis on the Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México (UNAM) and the Tecnológico de Monterrey.

In Brazil, the incorporation of CT into the school curriculum has also been a relevant agenda, especially after the inclusion of CT as one of the ten general competencies to be developed in Basic Education in the BNCC, launched by the Ministry of Education (MEC) in 2017. The "Guidelines for Teaching Computing in Basic Education", prepared by the SBC in 2018, highlights three axes: CT, Digital World, and Digital Culture, which provide a basis for the development of curricula and lesson plans that integrate computing into different areas of knowledge.

Furthermore, the SBC has promoted teacher training actions for the implementation of CT in Basic Education. Other institutions, such as the Instituto Ayrton Senna and the Centro de Inovação para a Educação Brasileira (CIEB), have also dedicated themselves to the theme and developed teaching materials and methodologies related to CT. Table 2 is a synthesis dedicated

to CT curricula in Latin America:

Tabela 2.3: CT Curricula in Latin America. Source: author, 2023.

Author	Year	Country	Work Title
Resende et al.	2020	Brazil	Competencies and skills of computational thinking: a study with Middle School Mathematics teachers
Lizárraga et al.	2019	Peru	Development of computational thinking skills in secondary education students in the city of Juliaca - Peru
Sánchez et al.	2021	Colombia	Implementation of a didactic intervention proposal for the development of computational thinking in Colombian basic secondary education
Vargas et al.	2021	Chile	Analysis of the contributions of the methodology based on computational thinking in the development of socio-emotional skills of primary education students in Chile
Costa et al.	2018	Brazil	Digital games as a strategy for the development of computational thinking in basic education children
Pérez et al.	2019	Mexico	Evaluation of a model for the development of computational thinking in primary school students through Scratch programming
Arbeláez et al.	2019	Colombia	Development of computational thinking in secondary education through video game programming in Scratch
Ramírez et al.	2020	Mexico	Development of computational thinking through educational robotics at the primary level. Case: "Leyes de Reforma" general preschool
Alcántara et al.	2019	Mexico	Computational thinking in solving mathematical problems in secondary school
González et al.	2019	Mexico	Design of a didactic model for the development of computational thinking in primary school children through the use of Scratch programming

In Brazil, the SBC and the *Centro de Inovação para a Educação Brasileira* (CIEB) appear as promoters of the inclusion of CT in Brazilian education. From 2017 to 2019, the SBC, with a commission appointed by the Council of Education, worked on the development of a document intended to be a formative benchmark in Computing for Basic Education.

They establish the competencies and skills that comprise Computing in Basic Education, from early childhood education to high school. As can be seen in Figure ??, these competencies and skills are separated into three axes: 1. CT, 2. Digital World, and 3. Digital Culture.

Figura 2.1: Computacional Thinking Axes and Skills Author: SBC, 2019.

On the other hand, CIEB, a non-profit organization created in 2016, supports public education networks by providing support to formulate public policies, develop concepts, prototyping, tools, and articulate specific agents for the Brazilian basic education system, Early Childhood Education and Elementary School. This support seeks to achieve a systemic transformation in learning processes, aiming for higher educational quality through the effective use of digital technologies. The organization is convinced that technology can generate quality, equity, and contemporaneity in education (RAABE et al., 2018).

To include computer science in the educational system, CIEB generated a reference curriculum for basic education, based on the SBC curriculum. As illustrated in Figure 2.2, this is also organized into three axes: 1. Digital Culture, 2. Computational Thinking, and 3. Digital Technology. These axes are subdivided into concepts, through which the curriculum is structured.

Figura 2.2: CIEB Reference Curriculum Author: CIEB, 2019.

It is also a document that proposes pedagogical practices, assessments, and materials that can be used in daily activities. The reference curriculum was developed considering the level of development that children should have acquired according to the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC). The BNCC highlights the importance of developing mathematical literacy and CT in Elementary School.

Furthermore, the Mathematics area, both in Elementary and High School, has as its central objective the understanding of mathematical concepts and procedures and the development of CT, aiming at solving and formulating problems in diverse contexts. Some states have already included the theme in their pedagogical proposal, but a joint effort by governments, schools, teachers, and society as a whole is necessary for CT to be effectively incorporated into the curriculum, having a methodology adequate for its practice.

Below is a timeline with the main milestones related to the teaching of computing in basic education in Brazil until the emergence of CT:

- 1970: Beginning of data processing teaching in technical schools and higher education in Brazil.
- 1980: Inclusion of informatics disciplines in technical and undergraduate course curricula.
- 1990: Creation of the National Program for Informatics in Education (ProInfo) by the Ministry of Education, aiming to promote digital inclusion and the use of technology in basic education.
- 2007: Publication of Law No. 11,645, which makes informatics teaching compulsory in basic education.
- 2008: Start of the One Computer per Student (UCA) program, which distributed laptops to public school students aiming to promote the use of technology in education.
- 2010: Launch of the National Education Plan (PNE) 2011-2020, which includes the goal of universalizing access to high-speed internet in schools and promoting the pedagogical use of information and communication technologies.
- 2012: Inclusion of informatics as a mandatory curricular component in the early years of elementary school.
- 2013: Launch of the Brazil More IT program by the Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation, aiming to train IT professionals and promote digital inclusion.
- 2014: Beginning of the discussion on the inclusion of CT in the Brazilian school curriculum.
- 2017: Publication of the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC), which includes CT as one of the ten general competencies to be developed in basic education.
- 2021: The Society for Computing Education (ACM SIGCSE) holds its annual conference from February 24 to 27.
- 2021: COVID-19 increases the need for computing and CT skills in many areas, including health and education.
- 2022: The National Council of Education (CNE) publishes Opinion CNE/CEB No. 2/2022, which defines the technology skills and competencies that students must acquire in Basic Education.
- 2022: Forecast for the implementation of the BNCC in all schools across the country, which should promote the teaching of CT on a large scale in Brazilian basic education.
- 2022: In October, Resolution CEB 01/2022 is published, which establishes the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) for Basic Education, including the importance of computational thinking.

- 2023: The National Digital Education Policy (PNED), Law No. 14,533, is approved in January, reinforcing the importance of digital inclusion and technology education in Brazilian schools.
- 2023: As of January 2023, the teaching of CT is still under development in Brazil. Some schools have already included the theme in their Mathematics and Science disciplines, but there is still no national policy for teaching CT in all basic education schools. The Ministry of Education has promoted initiatives for teacher training and the inclusion of the theme in curricula, but there is still a long way to go for CT to be effectively incorporated into Brazilian basic education.

We can highlight the most relevant points of the timeline that aimed to describe the important milestones in the history of the inclusion of digital education and CT in the Brazilian educational context. On February 17, 2022, Opinion CNE/CEB No. 2/2022 was published, which establishes the national curricular guidelines for digital education in basic education. This document becomes a reference for the implementation of CT in schools, bringing guidance on teacher training, the choice of resources and technologies, and the competencies and skills that must be developed by students.

On October 04, 2022, Resolution CEB 01/2022 was published, which establishes the General National Curricular Guidelines for Basic Education. This document provides guidance for the elaboration of curricula and defines the competencies and skills that students must develop at each stage of basic education, including CT. Therefore, a methodology that applies CT systematically and effectively is necessary in this implementation process.

To assist in the implementation of these guidelines, the Tables of Skills and Competencies were created, which detail the expected skills and competencies of students in each area of knowledge, including information and communication technology. In January 2023, the National Digital Education Policy (PNED) was sanctioned through Law No. 14,533, which aims to promote digital inclusion and the development of CT in basic education. This policy establishes goals and guidelines for the implementation of digital education in schools and for teacher training, in addition to providing for investments in technologies and infrastructure.

These legal and curricular milestones are fundamental for the promotion of CT in Brazilian basic education, as they establish clear guidelines for its implementation and integration into school curricula and methodologies. The development of CT can contribute significantly to the formation of more critical, creative students who are prepared to deal with the challenges and opportunities of the digital society.

2.5 The Integration Between Mental Processes and Computational Thinking

According to Lorenzato (2017), to increase the probability of learning success in the classroom, it is necessary to know who our students are, considering that they have their own characteristics, influences from different factors such as: cultural background, socioeconomic level, genetic heritage, and family education.

According to the author, it is essential for the child to master the seven basic mental processes for learning mathematics, which are: correspondence, comparison, classification, sequencing, seriation, inclusion, and conservation Lorenzato (2017).

Activities must be chosen, considering not only the children's characteristics but also their needs and the stage of cognitive development they are in, otherwise it will be like building the walls of a house without having prepared the foundation. The aforementioned author and professor also postulates that when the child does not perform more complex abstract conservations, they believe that the value of a variable changes based on its physical and/or spatial modifications. Therefore, when they do not believe that there can be different configurations for the same object, their mental structures are undergoing reasoning that comprises the pre-operational period or early childhood, which occurs from 2 to 7 years old, characterized by egocentrism, centration, and irreversibility, thus leading to discrepancies in the perception of causality.

The seven mental processes can be analogously correlated with the pillars of CT, namely, decomposition, pattern recognition, abstraction, algorithms, systemic thinking, testing and debugging, and creativity. When developed simultaneously, considering each brain structure mentioned here, it promotes the development of the child's logical reasoning, resulting in a new cognitive structure derived from CT. This process contributes to the child's cognitive and logical development, simultaneously preparing them for literacy in the digital world. The subsequent analysis examines the interconnection between the seven mental processes and the pillars of CT.

Correspondence: The ability to establish correspondences between objects or events finds a parallel in pattern recognition in CT. In this context, in computer science and programming, one identifies regularities and trends in data sets, resembling the mentioned correspondence skill.

Comparison: The ability to compare different objects or events can be associated with abstraction in CT. Here, in computer science and programming, one identifies common characteristics between different problems, resembling the outlined comparison capacity. **Classification:** The

ability to classify objects or events into categories is related to both abstraction and algorithms in CT. In computer science and programming, one categorizes data into specific structures and develops algorithms to manipulate this data, reflecting the mentioned classification skill.

Sequencing: The ability to place objects or events in a logical order finds equivalence in CT algorithms. In computer science and programming, one conceives sequences of instructions that are executed in a specific order to solve problems, reflecting the outlined sequencing capacity.

Seriation: The ability to establish an order in a series of objects or events is related to sequencing and algorithms in CT. In computer science and programming, one develops algorithms operating on sequences of data or events, aligning with the mentioned seriation skill.

Inclusion: The ability to understand the relationship of parts to a whole is associated with both abstraction and algorithms in CT. In computer science and programming, one abstracts common characteristics from a set of problems and develops general solutions applicable to different parts of a whole, reflecting the mentioned inclusion skill.

Conservation: The ability to understand that a quantity remains constant, regardless of changes in its appearance, is associated with both abstraction and algorithms in CT. In computer science and programming, one abstracts essential characteristics of a problem and develops algorithms that preserve these characteristics in different stages of a process, resembling the mentioned conservation skill.

Table 3 illustrates the intersection between brain structures and the pillars of CT, highlighting the correspondence between mental processes and the pillars of CT, evidencing the interrelationship between cognitive structures and the foundations of CT, and examples of plugged and unplugged activities that can be explored respecting the child's logical reasoning.

Tabela 2.4: The seven mental processes and CT and their main pillars. Source: author, 2023.

Activity	Definition	Relation to CT	Practical Examples and Activities
Correspondence	The act of establishing a "one-to-one" relationship.	Decomposition: The act of breaking down a complex problem into smaller, more manageable parts.	Activity: "Puzzle": Each puzzle piece represents a smaller part, and students collaborate to assemble the complete picture. Online Activity: "Virtual Puzzle": Use of interactive apps or websites to solve online puzzles in teams.

Activity	Definition	Relation to CT	Practical Examples and Activities
Comparison	The act of establishing differences or similarities.	Pattern Recognition: Identifying regularities and trends in data or situations.	Activity: "Visual Patterns": Students observe sequences of shapes and colors to identify patterns and determine the next figure in the sequence. Online Activity: "Pattern Game": Use of online games that challenge students to identify patterns in a digital interface.
Classification	The act of separating into categories according to similarities or differences.	Abstraction: Simplifying a problem by isolating only the essential details and ignoring irrelevant information.	Activity: "Organizing Objects": Students organize a variety of objects into categories based on specific characteristics. Online Activity: "Interactive Classification": Use of digital tools that allow students to classify and organize objects virtually.
Sequencing	The act of making one element succeed another without considering the order between them.	Algorithm: Developing a logical sequence of steps to solve a problem or execute a task.	Activity: "Cookie Recipe": Students create a sequence of steps to make cookies, emphasizing the importance of the order of instructions. Online Activity: "Programming Recipes": Use of visual programming tools to create algorithms for virtual recipes.
Seriation	The act of ordering a sequence according to a criterion.	Systemic Thinking: Understanding how parts interact in a system and how changes in one part affect the whole.	Activity: "Building a System": Students collaborate to create a simple system, such as a gear model, understanding how each part contributes to the functioning of the whole. Online Activity: "System Simulation": Use of online simulations to explore how different parts affect a system.

Activity	Definition	Relation to CT	Practical Examples and Activities
Inclusion	The act of encompassing one set by another.	Testing and Debugging: Evaluating and correcting errors in a program or process.	Activity: "Error Hunt": Students identify and correct "errors" in a story or number sequence, promoting critical thinking. Online Activity: "Debugging Challenge": Use of online challenges to debug codes or logical sequences.
Conservation	The act of perceiving that quantity does not depend on arrangement, shape, or position.	Creativity: Using imagination to find innovative solutions and think outside established patterns.	Activity: "Paper Innovation": Students create innovative ways to fold and cut paper to highlight that the amount of paper does not change with its shape. Online Activity: "Digital Creative Challenge": Use of digital tools to create innovative creative projects.
Numerical Insertion	Understanding the inclusion of elements in sets, an essential notion for comprehending the meaning of numbers.	Not Applicable	Activity: "Exploring Numbers": Students group elements into sets and explore how different sets can be included in larger sets, introducing basic numerical concepts. Online Activity: "Numerical Inclusion Game": Use of online games to explore the inclusion of numbers in sets.

By combining CT with the mental processes developed by Lorenzato (2017), children are encouraged to think inventively, solve problems in a structured manner, and develop analysis and synthesis skills. This approach provides a solid foundation for learning, as it stimulates logical reasoning and structured thinking based on the pillars of CT. To understand, use, and create digital information and communication technologies critically, meaningfully, reflectively, and ethically in various social practices (including school practices) to communicate, access and disseminate information, produce knowledge, solve problems, and exercise protagonism and authorship in personal and collective life da Educação (2018).

Nowadays, we see the individual as responsible for their own learning, who reflects and creates knowledge based on their experience. This individual is unique but is also composed of multiple

dimensions, including emotions, motor skills, cognitive, sensory, neural, and ethical abilities. Therefore, it is important to understand all these layers of personality and offer an education that considers all these dimensions of the human being. There will be no progress in education without simultaneously considering the emotional and cognitive facets of the brain. The union of these two powers—neuroscience and CT—in education not only potentiates the child’s cognitive development but also prepares them for the current and future demands of a society increasingly immersed in the technological era.

2.6 Neuroscience and Learning

Knowledge from neuroscience makes it possible to inform education about how the brain learns and tends to be more efficient, but not to explain or provide prescriptions and/or recipes that guarantee results or propose a new pedagogy. Recent studies using magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scanning devices have revealed that learning indeed has its basis in neuroscience Lent (2019). This means that learning can be better understood when examined in the light of this science. In particular, it can help explain how the brain processes and stores information, how memory is formed, and how neurons connect to create associations from their interaction with the environment or object of knowledge. The detailed wiring diagram of the human brain is not pre-programmed as in most animals. Our machinery models itself by interacting with the world. This information is important when thinking about training and learning, considering that the brain molds itself based on the experiences the subject undergoes Eagleman (2022).

It can be inferred from the above that the use of appropriate strategies in an educational process that is creative and engaging will result in changes in the quantity and quality of synaptic connections.

Corroborating this line of thought, Simões and Nogaro (2016) emphasizes that learning is conditioned by the possibilities of the environment; thus, each subject’s experiences determine the numerous learnings, skills, and competencies they can develop.

Although most changes are too small to be detected with the naked eye, everything an individual has lived and lives alters the physical structure of their brain, from gene expression to the positions of molecules and the architecture of neurons. These microscopic and indelible impressions accumulate and sculpt the brain, making the individual who they are and who they can become, Eagleman (2019). Therefore, when the individual, even for a brief moment, interacts with the environment, some aspect of this interaction remains stored in their brain, and what will impact the nature of this interaction is how much meaning the information holds. And what has meaning? That which generates an emotion in us.

Lent (2019) points out that learning involves an individual with their brain capturing information from the environment, storing it for a time, and eventually using it to guide their subsequent behavior. The brain's capacity to transform itself in a child and, to a lesser degree, in an adolescent is substantially greater than in an adult, this is because, mainly in childhood and adolescence, this brain is biologically more plastic, biologically more malleable. Campos et al. (2014)

Studies and research in neuroscience solidify the principles of learning through countless studies. These studies demonstrate how the act of learning modifies the structures and functions of the brain. Therefore, knowledge encompasses not only the ability to retain information but also the potential to recall and apply accurate information in diverse contexts Oliveira (2011).

This understanding of the basic mechanisms of learning assists education in developing new teaching methods that are coherent with the child's prior aptitudes and skills, and their potential to learn.

Dehaene (2022b) highlights that we know a lot about how learning works. Thirty years of research at the interdisciplinary boundaries of computer science, neurobiology, and cognitive psychology have broadly clarified the algorithms used by our brain, the circuits involved, and the factors that affect their effectiveness.

According to Kaku (2014), parallel processing is one of the keys to our brain's functioning. When a magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) brain scan is performed, one can discover how and how much the brain thinks, as it is possible to see from this scan the various brain areas being activated simultaneously, indicating that the brain divides a task into smaller parts and processes them concurrently. This indicates that the brain processes tasks by dividing them into smaller sub-processes and operating concomitantly, corroborating the previously discussed pillars of CT.

The conceptions of Wing (2006) about CT can be related to this neurocognitive phenomenon. By defining CT as a skill involving problem-solving, decomposing complex tasks into smaller parts, pattern recognition, and abstraction, it highlights the similarity between the brain processing identified in MRI scans and the principles of CT.

On the other hand, Papert (1980), in developing the theory of knowledge construction through programming (known as constructionism), argues that learning is more effective when students are engaged in practical projects, in which they need to decompose complex problems into smaller tasks to create solutions. This approach, based on the active manipulation of concepts and the construction of artifacts, also aligns with the idea of parallel processing in the brain, emphasizing the importance of simultaneously addressing different aspects of a task.

Thus, the conceptions of Wing and Papert on CT converge with the understanding of processing in the brain, reinforcing the importance of problem decomposition and the simultaneous approach of sub-processes in the efficient resolution of cognitive challenges and real-world problems.

2.7 Development of Computational Thinking in the Light of Neuroscience

Naturally, the emerging science that studies how we learn is especially relevant for all those who deal professionally with learning, Dehaene (2022b). According to Cosenza and Guerra (2011), the younger the individual understands logic, the better their brain will work with everyday issues. In this context, Cynthia Solomon's ideas on teaching computing to children align parallelly with these perspectives. The aforementioned researcher emphasizes the importance of practical and exploratory approaches in teaching computing to children, advocating the idea that they learn best when involved in practical and creative activities, especially those related to computer programming. Furthermore, she believes that programming can be a powerful tool for promoting logical thinking, problem-solving, and creative expression from an early age. Liukas (2015) emphasizes the idea that programming is more than just writing code, but a tool for expressing ideas and solving problems, highlighting the idea of uniting creativity with logic, encouraging children to develop important cognitive skills from an early age. Piaget (1970) emphasizes that the individual acts only when experiencing a need, that is, if the balance between the environment and the organism is momentarily broken, in this case, the action tends to reestablish the equilibrium, that is, precisely to readapt the organism.

It can be inferred from the elucidation that in the process of assimilation, accommodation, and consolidation of learning and memory, there is another process termed by Piaget as disequilibrium or cognitive conflict, which consists of the instability of knowledge when an intellectual challenge presents itself to the individual, and the organism (brain) seeks strategies, constructing new mental structures, susceptible to applying to the environment, resulting in a stable system. It is worth emphasizing that this process of assimilating, accommodating, disequilibrating, and organizing occurs in all stages of human development as described by the theory of Genetic Epistemology by the biologist and psychologist Jean Piaget. The table below presents, in a synthesized manner, the developmental stages proposed by the author.

Tabela 2.5: Description of the developmental stages developed by Jean Piaget. Source: author, 2023

Developmental Stage	Age Range	Characteristics
Sensorimotor	0 to 2	Evolution of perception and motor skills
Pre-operational	2 to 7	Internalization of action schemes, emergence of language, symbolism, and deferred imitation.
Concrete Operational	7 to 11	Construction and cognitive decentration; understanding of reversibility without coordination of it; seriation, classification, and simple compensation.
Formal Operational	Above 11	Development of mathematical and infralogical logical operations, complex compensation (logic), and probability (inclusion of laws).

Piaget (1955) emphasized that learning occurs when children are challenged with problems that are within their stage of cognitive development, problems that are proportional to their neural structures but require some effort and overcoming of their reasoning to solve. Furthermore, according to Piaget, it is through solving challenging problems that children construct new mental schemas and develop new skills and competencies. We can verify from the aforementioned contributions that learning requires attention and engagement from the student; this also requires a resonant educator, who proposes challenges that consider the child's developmental stage and their competence to solve the proposed challenge, in a manner coherent with their capacity and aptitude. Engagement, in turn, has two variables: challenge - everything is a challenge, educating, lecturing, public speaking, relating, everything is a challenge for the brain. However, our challenges will find their competencies. If a challenge is too great for an individual's competencies, they enter a process of stress and anxiety. If a challenge is too small for their competencies, then it promotes boredom and demotivation.

Figura 2.3: Learning, Competence, and Challenge. Source: author, 2023.

The graph above is a useful representation for understanding the relationship between challenge and competence in learning, as discussed by the theorists mentioned above. Such contributions support the development of the teaching methodology focused on the development of CT in basic education. Based on scientific works focused on the study of the mind's functioning, executive functions (EF), and cognition, combined with good practices and pedagogical projects, it is feasible to conceive an appropriate CT teaching model capable of fostering opportunities for protagonism in one's own learning and for producing science and technologies. Furthermore, such an approach promotes a new way of thinking, involving effective strategies in problem-solving, critical and creative thinking, grounded in the principles and pillars of CT, making the new generation or new humanity fit for present and future challenges in an increasingly technological society. According to Neuropediatrician Dr. Arruda (2024), coordinator of the School of Diversity Project and director of Instituto Glia: "Executive Functions (EF) develop from birth until early adulthood and allow the individual to perform voluntary actions with autonomy and organization to achieve specific goals, hence their fundamental importance for behavior and school performance". According to Corigliano (2024), executive functions involve various types of skills; researchers recognize three main dimensions: Working Memory, Inhibitory Control, and Cognitive Flexibility, while others subdivide them into more items. The development of these skills is important to empower the child cognitively, socially, and emotionally. Skills for EF emerge from early childhood. At each stage, the child acquires more skills and develops appropriate behaviors. The development of EF occurs through the gradual

internalization of the "what, how, and why". A very similar form is the Three-Period Lesson, developed by Séguin and Montessori (2020) and refined by Maria Montessori. This process consists of presenting new concepts and their vocabulary in a way that leads the child to think about the object, interpret it, and subsequently make use of this information. In summary, the child awakens, develops, and expands their knowledge in relation to the proposed object of study, evidencing the effectiveness of the methodology employed in fostering CT as a necessary cognitive skill in contemporaneidade

2.8 Problem-Based Learning Methodology: An Innovative Approach in Education

Problem-Based Learning (PBL) emerges as an innovative educational methodology that places students at the center of the learning process, encouraging autonomy, the practical application of knowledge, and the development of critical skills. This method, grounded in solid pedagogical principles, has received growing attention from researchers and educators.

PBL is an approach that, according to Barkley (2008), starts from the premise that learning is more effective when students are challenged by authentic problems that mirror real-world situations. In this context, Savin-Baden and Major (2004) emphasize that PBL not only promotes the understanding of specific content but also develops problem-solving skills, critical thinking, and teamwork.

Jean Piaget and John Dewey, cited by Jonassen and Land (2000), provide essential theoretical foundations for PBL by emphasizing the importance of contextualized and meaningful learning. PBL integrates harmoniously with constructivist theory, advocating that learning is an active process where students construct knowledge from their experiences and interactions.

Resnick et al. (2007), influential in the field of computational education, highlights the relevance of PBL in the context of CT development. He argues that by facing challenging problems, students are prompted to think algorithmically, decompose problems into smaller parts, and create effective solutions.

According to Hmelo-Silver (2004), PBL is not just a teaching technique but an approach that promotes a paradigmatic shift in education, focusing on the student as an active and participatory learner, constructing meaning in a collaborative learning environment.

By adopting PBL, educators are not just facilitators of the process but co-researchers, guiding students in the active search for solutions and encouraging independent investigation Wood (2003). Leitão (2012) emphasizes the importance of teacher mediation in this process,

highlighting that the teacher plays a crucial role in guiding and supporting students in the construction of knowledge.

In the current and future context of society, there is a demand for professionals to have practical training combined with multidisciplinary competencies. The ability to solve problems similarly constitutes a significant portion of performance in the corporate environment. Given this scenario, the adoption of problem-based learning emerges as an extremely relevant and enriching methodology. This approach contributes significantly to the development of a variety of competencies and skills that are essential for the student, especially when transcending the boundaries of their formal educational trajectory, some of which are explicit in the table below:

Tabela 2.6: Competencies and Skills Developed through Problem-Based Learning. Source: author, 2023

Skill/Competency	Description
Development of Autonomy	By engaging students through projects, the methodology promotes autonomy, encouraging critical discussions and the connection between disciplines and experiences to solve presented problems.
Increased Engagement	The practical activities proposed by the methodology stimulate interaction among students, making classes more dynamic and enjoyable.
Teamwork	The methodology strengthens teamwork, as students depend on each other to reach a solution, requiring compromises and valuing different opinions during the process.
Interdisciplinarity	By bringing problems that involve and mix concepts from different subjects, the methodology promotes interdisciplinarity in the classroom.

In summary, PBL, grounded in constructivist principles, challenges the traditional teacher-centered educational approach, placing students at the epicenter of the learning process. By promoting the resolution of authentic problems, this methodology not only facilitates the assimilation of content but also develops essential skills for the 21st century. The convergence of different theories and the practical application of this approach indicate a transformative potential in the educational field, preparing students to face the complex and dynamic challenges of contemporary society.

2.9 Considerations from the Systematic Literature Review

The systematic literature review conducted allowed for a better understanding of the development of CT globally and its application in the Brazilian context. It was possible to identify that the concept of CT is based on fundamental cognitive skills, such as problem-solving, logical reasoning, and abstraction. Regarding CT curricula, it is important to highlight that most countries that included the theme in elementary education did so in a cross-curricular manner, that is, incorporating it into other subjects. This is due to the interdisciplinary nature of CT, which allows its application in diverse areas of knowledge.

However, despite identifying the cognitive processes involved in CT activities, none of the articles in this systematic review made a connection with how the brain learns, that is, with the neuroscience of learning and how CT can contribute to its development.

From the SLR, it is pertinent to affirm the three main approaches mentioned by Bocconi et al. (2016) when it comes to incorporating CT skills into compulsory education curricula:

- As a cross-curricular theme — basic Computer Science concepts are addressed in all subjects, and all teachers are responsible for developing CT skills;
- As a separate subject — the basic concepts of CS and CT are taught in a subject related to computing (e.g., Informatics);
- Within other subjects — the basic concepts of CS and CT are integrated into other subjects in the curriculum (e.g., Mathematics and Technology as described in the BNCC).

Based on the approaches presented by Bocconi et al. (2016) for incorporating CT skills into compulsory education curricula, it is possible to observe the need for an integrated and interdisciplinary approach for its application.

The cross-curricular approach can provide the insertion of CT into different subjects, making it a common element to all of them. The approach of a separate subject, such as Informatics, can restrict access to CT, limiting its application to a single area of knowledge.

Finally, the approach within other subjects can offer the opportunity to connect CT with different areas, providing more meaningful and contextualized learning. Based on this analysis, the next section will present the procedures adopted for conducting the systematic literature review, as well as the search strategies, article selection criteria, and data analysis.

Teaching Methodology for CT Through the Development of Game Design Document (GDD) with a PBL Approach

The teaching of CT in basic education has proven to be a powerful strategy for developing cognitive skills and preparing students for the challenges of the 21st century. The creation of digital games, when structured through design documents (GDD), offers a practical and dynamic context for applying the four pillars of CT: decomposition, pattern recognition, abstraction, and algorithms. Combined with Problem-Based Learning (PBL), this approach provides an effective methodology that not only engages students but also empowers them to solve problems systematically and creatively. Several studies have shown that the combination of PBL with the development of digital games can significantly improve student performance in skills related to logic and programming (Nipo and Nunes (2024); Dos Santos Silva, Diniz, and França (2019)). This chapter presents a methodology for teaching CT in the early years of elementary school, based on the use of GDDs and the PBL approach, allowing students to develop computational competencies and solve real-world problems.

3.1 Proposed Methodology

The proposed methodology combines the principles of CT with the stages of digital game development, using the GDD structure as a planning tool. Problem-Based Learning (PBL) acts as the central pedagogical approach, in which students are challenged to solve complex problems through the creation of a digital game, focusing on real and contemporary issues, such as environmental, social, or other problems, as illustrated in Figure 3.1 below.

Figura 3.1: Integrated Methodology. Source: author, 2024

The methodology consists of three main stages: Exploration and Introduction, Planning and Development, and Evaluation and Reflection. Exploration and Introduction introduce the pillars of CT through practical activities that illustrate each concept, suggesting the division of complex tasks into smaller parts, such as planning a daily schedule or organizing the stages of a game; the identification of similarities and differences, such as finding common elements among digital games they already know; focusing on the essential aspects of a problem, leaving aside irrelevant details. For example, asking them to represent game characters with simple geometric figures and solving problems, such as creating instructions for a character’s movement in a fictional game. These introductory activities prepare students for the application of CT concepts in GDD development. Furthermore, the central problem of the PBL approach is presented at this stage, serving as a guide for the next phases. In the Planning and Development stage, the GDD is used as the central tool. The document organizes and structures the creative process, allowing students to plan all elements of the digital game, from the narrative to the interaction mechanics. The authors, organized into groups, begin by defining the game’s plot, connecting it to the problem presented in the previous stage. Characters, scenarios, and challenges that reflect the central theme are developed, using flowcharts and diagrams to map interactions and mechanics. Ideas are transformed into algorithms, logically and sequentially representing the actions that the game characters must perform. The construction of the GDD favors

pattern recognition and abstraction, as students need to identify common elements to avoid redundancies and simplify the design. They also have the opportunity to test initial game prototypes and review the structures planned in the GDD, applying improvements iteratively. In the Evaluation and Reflection stage, the developed games are presented, and a self-assessment is conducted based on the initially established objectives. The evaluation is structured in two moments:

- 1. Group Evaluation:** reflection on the team's performance, the quality of the solutions implemented in the game, and the learnings obtained during the process.
- 2. External Evaluation:** feedback from peers and teachers on the effectiveness of the game in addressing the central problem proposed by PBL. Additionally, reflection on the application of the CT pillars throughout the project development is stimulated, thus consolidating the acquired learning.

3.2 Adaptations for Students with Special Educational Needs

The proposed methodology for teaching CT in the early years of Elementary School seeks to encompass the diversity of learning profiles, including students with special educational needs (SEN). According to the Brazilian Inclusion Law *Brazilian Inclusion Law* (2015) and the guidelines of the National Common Curricular Base [?], it is imperative to ensure that pedagogical practices are accessible to all students, respecting their specificities and promoting educational equity. The integration of the Game Design Document (GDD) and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) allows for the adaptation of activities and tools to the needs of students with different disabilities, ensuring their active participation in the learning process. The proposed adaptations are described below:

Adaptations for Students with Intellectual Disabilities: Simplified practical activities, structured in smaller steps, with visual or oral instructions to aid comprehension ^{??}. Representation of the GDD through drawings or figures instead of more complex textual descriptions.

Adaptations for Students with Visual Impairments: Use of tactile materials, such as relief boards and physical representations of algorithms, to introduce concepts like patterns and sequences. Technological tools with screen readers, such as NVDA (NonVisual Desktop Access), can be incorporated Araújo and et al. (2019).

Adaptations for Students with Hearing Impairments: Prioritization of visual resources, such as flowcharts and icons in the GDD. Use of subtitled videos and Libras (Brazilian Sign Language) mediators for communicating concepts and steps de Quadros and Schmiedt (2006).

Adaptations for Students with ADHD or Focus Difficulties: Short, dynamic, and interactive activities to maintain student interest and engagement. Immediate rewards and constant feedback as positive stimuli ?. Furthermore, collaborative work plays a crucial role in inclusion, promoting interaction between students with and without SEN. Heterogeneous groups are organized to value the individual skills of each student, enabling meaningful contributions to the development of the GDD and the game. The inclusion of unplugged activities, such as games and physical representations of algorithms, is also an effective strategy. According to Papert (1980), practices that connect learning to tangible and meaningful contexts facilitate cognitive and social development, especially for students with difficulties.

3.3 Methodological Foundation and Applied Model

Development of Computational Thinking

As mentioned earlier, the concept of CT was initially popularized by Wing (2006), who describes CT as an essential competency comparable to reading and writing. Subsequent studies have shown that the development of CT from the early grades can foster skills such as problem-solving, decomposition, and abstraction, which are useful not only in computing but in various areas of knowledge Wing (2008); Grover and Pea (2018). Research has shown that the creation of practical environments, such as digital game development, can accelerate the learning of CT in children and young people. According to Kafai (2006), the use of platforms like Scratch has facilitated the introduction of computational concepts in a playful and creative manner, promoting greater knowledge retention and student engagement. Studies conducted by Israel-Fishelson et al. (2021) suggest that when students are encouraged to apply the pillars of CT in practical contexts, such as game creation, cognitive development is more robust, promoting greater capacity for abstraction and solving complex problems.

3.4 Integration of the Pillars of Computational Thinking

The proposed methodology aims to integrate the pillars of CT – decomposition, pattern recognition, abstraction, and algorithms – into the stages of creating the GDD for digital games. This process seeks to offer students a practical and interdisciplinary approach to the development of cognitive skills and competencies. Each pillar of CT is applied contextually during the planning and development phases of the GDD, providing a structured didactic experience connected to the skills necessary for game creation. The application of each pillar in the GDD context is detailed below:

Decomposition: This pillar involves dividing a complex problem or task into smaller, more manageable parts. In the context of GDD creation, students are encouraged to plan the basic structure of the game, identifying elements such as characters, scenarios, objectives, and mechanics. For example, the main components of a game level can be listed and broken down into specific tasks, such as drawing the scenario, programming character movements, and creating challenges.

Pattern Recognition: Involves identifying similarities, differences, and regularities in data or problems. In the application to the GDD, students perform exercises to recognize patterns in elements of known games, such as scoring mechanics, enemy behaviors, or level structure. This process helps create a solid reference base for game development and to avoid redundancies or inconsistencies in the proposal.

Abstraction: Refers to the ability to represent a problem or system in a simplified form, focusing on essential aspects and eliminating irrelevant details. During GDD creation, students are guided to represent key game concepts clearly and objectively, such as summarizing the narrative in a synopsis or simplifying the main mechanics with schemes or diagrams that demonstrate the basic interactions between elements.

Algorithm: Consists of elaborating sequences of logical and organized steps for problem-solving or task execution. In the GDD, students develop algorithms for the main game actions, such as the instructions that determine a character's movements or the rules for interaction with objects in the scenario. An example could be creating flowcharts that represent the functioning of a level or the conditions for victory and defeat. Figure 4.3 presents an illustrative diagram of the integration of the CT pillars in GDD creation, highlighting the relationship between theoretical concepts and their respective practical applications.

Figura 3.2: Diagram of the Integration of Computational Thinking Pillars in the GDD. Source: author.

3.5 Use of GDD (Game Design Document)

The use of Game Design Documents (GDD) in educational environments has proven to be an effective strategy for promoting systematic thinking and structured planning. According to Shute et al. (2017), the GDD allows students to organize their ideas and create a clear roadmap for implementing their solutions, promoting the development of algorithms and the application of CT concepts. Corradini et al. (2017) highlight that the use of GDD in the game creation process increases student autonomy, helping them visualize the entire workflow involved in software development, which includes everything from plot elaboration to the implementation of game algorithms. The literature also suggests that the development of

GDDs can improve skills related to critical thinking and teamwork. Grover and Pea (2018) show that collaboration among students during the creation of a GDD stimulates the exchange of ideas and the refinement of proposed solutions, resulting in deeper and more meaningful learning.

Planning and Development of the GDD (Game Design Document)

The Game Design Document (GDD) is employed as a central tool to structure and organize the creative process in digital game development. This document allows students to plan and document all elements of the game, from the narrative to the interaction mechanics, promoting a clear understanding of the workflow and the steps necessary for project implementation. In the educational context, students, organized into groups, begin the process by defining the game's plot, connecting it to the problem presented in the previous stage, usually within the scope of the PBL (Problem-Based Learning) methodology. This approach allows for the contextualization of the central theme, ensuring that the game is not only a creative product but also a reflection of the issues studied. Figure 3.3 of the following mind map visually illustrates the three stages of GDD planning and development, highlighting the essential elements and their connections.

Figura 3.3: Mind map with the planning stages. Source: author

3.6 Proposed GDD Model for Early Years of Elementary School

Pattern Recognition: during GDD creation, students identify common elements and mechanics in known games, applying these references to avoid duplications or inconsistencies in the design.

Algorithms: ideas are transformed into logical and organized sequences, which define the actions and behaviors of the characters in the game. This step helps them understand and develop clear and well-defined action flows.

Abstraction and Collaboration: in addition to focusing on the essential aspects of the game, the construction of the GDD promotes a collaborative environment where students discuss ideas, resolve conflicts, develop cognitively, and learn to work as a team.

Iteration and Revision: after the initial planning, students have the opportunity to test game prototypes, identifying flaws or points for improvement. This iterative cycle allows for reviewing and refining the structures documented in the GDD, consolidating problem-solving and structured planning skills.

The construction of the GDD develops logical and cognitive sense, allowing them to visualize the workflow and make changes as needed. The process also promotes the development of fundamental skills in concept abstraction and programming logic. Figure 3.4 illustrates the GDD development model, which will be used by the children as a planning guide. The model highlights the main stages of the process and evidences the integration with the CT pillars, facilitating the practical application of the concepts.

Figura 3.4: GDD Development Model). Source: author

3.7 Application of Problem-Based Learning (PBL)

The methodology is based on the PBL approach, which will be deepened in the stages of the game creation project as described below:

Problem Introduction - the project will begin with the presentation of a real problem (social, environmental, cultural, or other), which the students must solve through the game. For example, if the theme is sustainability, the development of a game that demonstrates how daily choices impact the environment will be proposed. In the research and development process, they will identify the problem, research possible solutions, and outline how the game can address the presented problem.

Research and Development Phase - during the game development process, the PBL approach will be applied through activities involving problem exploration. This will include discussions about the implications of the chosen theme, interviews with experts, or additional research to substantiate how the game will offer a creative solution. In this stage, problem-solving will be the central focus, while game construction will function as the practical solution.

Evaluation and Reflection - in the final phase, PBL will be incorporated into the project evaluation and reflection. Upon completing the game, they will be able to conduct a group analysis and discussion to evaluate how the game addresses the proposed problem, identify possible improvements, and reflect on how the CT pillars contributed to the creation of the solution. These three elements play a fundamental role in the process of assimilation and consolidation of both the concepts and practices involved.

3.8 Considerations on Technologies and Tools

The choice of appropriate technologies and tools is essential for the effective implementation of the proposed methodology, especially in the context of teaching CT and creating digital games in the fifth grade of elementary school. In this sense, platforms were selected that balance accessibility, engagement, and practical applicability, considering both the pedagogical objectives and the expected level of technological proficiency for this age group.

Scratch T. S. Team (2024) is widely recognized as one of the most suitable tools for introducing programming and game design concepts in a visual and interactive way. Its block-based code interface allows students to experiment with logic, events, and interactions intuitively. In the context of planning and developing the Game Design Document (GDD), Scratch will be used for the initial prototyping of games, enabling the practical application of algorithms, abstractions,

and pattern recognition.

Godot G. E. Team (2024) is an open-source and free game engine, widely used for the development of 2D and 3D games. Launched in 2014 by OKAM Studio, Godot stands out for its flexibility, intuitive interface, and support for multiple platforms. It is known for its reduced learning curve, making it accessible to both beginners and experienced developers. Its visual interface is simple and straightforward, allowing non-technical users to also interact with the tool. Furthermore, the engine is constantly evolving, with regular updates introducing new features and improvements.

MakeCode Arcade The M. M. Team (2024) platform, developed by Microsoft, offers a friendly environment for creating 2D games focused on basic programming concepts and retro (pixel art) design. Through this tool, students will be able to explore programming logic and create games that emphasize problem-solving and the development of simple mechanics, such as character movement and interactions with objects.

CoSpaces Edu C. E. Team (2024) is a platform aimed at creating interactive 3D worlds and virtual reality (VR). It will be used for students to develop scenarios and environments that complement the narratives created in the GDD. This tool also offers the opportunity to integrate programming elements, allowing students to experiment with more complex interactions in their games. The immersive experience provided by CoSpaces Edu promotes creative engagement and broadens the understanding of game design.

Gamefroot G. Team (2024) is an online platform that allows the creation of 2D games with a friendly interface and support for collaborative work. Within the scope of the GDD, the tool will be used for building more detailed narratives and for mapping game interactions and mechanics, based on the diagrams and flowcharts developed during the initial stages. Furthermore, the possibility of group work on the platform facilitates the application of collaborative and iterative dynamics.

These platforms were selected due to their compatibility with the cognitive and technical level of fifth-grade students and their ability to explore the pillars of CT (decomposition, pattern recognition, abstraction, and algorithms). Moreover, their implementation in the school environment requires few technological resources, needing only the availability of computers or mobile devices with internet access. The diversity of platforms allows for greater diversity and complexity in game creation, promoting scalable learning adapted to their skills. Furthermore, the use of these tools expands the children's technological repertoire, preparing them to interact with more advanced technologies in the present and future. This technological approach ensures that students develop competencies in a practical and creative way, consolidating CT and collaborative concepts. The implementation of practices involving the teaching of

CT and the creation of Game Design Documents (GDDs) in schools lacking internet and digital devices requires the adaptation of methodologies to available resources, prioritizing unplugged approaches and accessible materials. These strategies allow the development of fundamental skills, such as problem-solving, creativity, and teamwork, to be worked on in a meaningful and inclusive way. The use of simple and accessible materials, such as paper, cardboard, bottle caps, and other recycled resources, is a viable solution for simulating elements of digital game design. For example, flowcharts, interaction maps, and algorithms can be elaborated on posters or paper cards, allowing students to draw and manipulate game elements manually. Furthermore, manipulable pieces, such as bottle caps and sticks, can be used to represent characters, scenarios, and interaction mechanics, encouraging hands-on learning and the understanding of concepts like abstraction and algorithms. In the absence of technology, the elaboration of the GDD can be done manually. Students can write the game's plot, detail the characters and scenarios in notebooks or sheets of paper, and plan the game mechanics using diagrams, flowcharts, or drawings on cardboard. This approach explores skills such as abstraction and pattern recognition, encouraging students to identify key elements and avoid redundancies in the design. The manual GDD development stage promotes teamwork, with students being encouraged to assume different roles within the groups, such as scriptwriters, illustrators, or mechanics planners. The use of physical prototypes, such as cardboard models, allows for the initial validation of game ideas. The review process is carried out collectively, with groups presenting their projects to the class, receiving feedback, and applying improvements interactively.

CHAPTER 4

Materials and Methods

The development of this research was based on a methodological approach grounded in a systematic literature review and the proposition of a teaching methodology applied to the development of Computational Thinking (CT) in the early years of Elementary School. The materials and methodological procedures adopted are detailed below:

1. Materials

The materials used for conducting the research were organized into three main categories:

1.1. Theoretical References:

Scientific studies on Computational Thinking, Problem-Based Learning (PBL), and Game Design Document (GDD). Educational guidelines, such as the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC) and CNE/CP Resolutions 02/2017 and CNE/CP 04/2018. Neuroscientific evidence related to learning in the early stages of children's cognitive development.

1.2. Planning and Application Tools:

Game Design Document (GDD) model adapted to the pedagogical needs of elementary school. Digital game development platforms, such as Scratch, MakeCode Arcade, CoSpaces Edu, and Gamefroot, selected for their accessibility and suitability for the age group.

1.3. Data Collection and Organization Instruments:

Criteria and parameters for the analysis of studies in the systematic literature review. Structuring of frameworks and tables to synthesize the review results and categorize practical applications.

2. Methods

The methodology was structured into two main stages:

2.1. Systematic Literature Review:

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were established for the selection of relevant studies on Computational Thinking, prioritizing scientific articles indexed in recognized databases. The analysis

focused on identifying key concepts, pedagogical approaches, and methodologies that support the teaching of CT in Basic Education. The results were organized into thematic categories, highlighting theoretical and practical contributions to the field.

2.2. Proposition of the Teaching Methodology:

The methodology was developed based on the following steps: Structuring of the Teaching Model: Integration of the Computational Thinking pillars (decomposition, patterns, abstraction, and algorithms) with the development of GDDs, using PBL as the central pedagogical approach.

Definition of Planning Stages:

Construction of a structured process that includes problem introduction, GDD planning and development, and reflective evaluation.

Consideration of Technological Inclusion:

Adaptation of the proposal for diverse educational contexts, including unplugged computing for schools with limited access to technological resources.

3. Theoretical Validation

The methodology was analyzed in light of previously published studies, educational guidelines, and theoretical principles of Genetic Epistemology, as well as neuroscientific evidence that supports the practical application of the approach in children's cognitive development.

CHAPTER 5

Results

The proposed methodology, which integrates Computational Thinking, GDD, and PBL, focuses on the development of advanced cognitive skills, such as complex problem-solving, algorithmic thinking, and abstraction capacity. It is expected that students who participate in this methodology will demonstrate greater capacity for project planning and execution, in addition to a deeper understanding of computational principles and how to apply them in different contexts. According to studies conducted by Haseski et al. (2018), the integration of PBL with digital game creation results in greater knowledge retention and more advanced development of computational skills. The research by Pérez-Marína et al. (2020) reinforces these findings, demonstrating that students who participated in projects based on PBL and GDD showed significant improvements in their ability to solve problems and work in teams.

The integration of Computational Thinking into the curriculum of the early years of elementary education is an urgent need to prepare children and young people from their basic education for the challenges of the 21st century. By using GDDs as a planning tool and PBL as a pedagogical approach, this methodology provides a practical and engaging way to teach Computational Thinking. Furthermore, the creation of digital games not only motivates students but also offers a rich environment for the development of cognitive, social, computational, and emotional skills.

6.1 Suggestions for Future Work

To ensure the effectiveness of this methodology, future studies should focus on evaluating its implementation in different educational contexts, exploring how the proposal can be adapted to various educational levels and areas of knowledge.

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